

Effect of Organisational Justice on Employees' Job Satisfaction in Higher Educational Institutions of Gombe State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study is to examine the effect of Organizational Justice on Employee Job Satisfaction at Gombe State Higher Educational Institutions (HEI). Four research questions and four objectives were designed to capture the essence of this study. This study used variables such as distributive justice, procedural justice, interactive justice, compensation as proxies that measure organizational justice and employee job satisfaction. The research was conducted among teaching and non-teaching staff of Gombe State Higher Educational Institutions (HEI). Literature was reviewed on job satisfaction, organizational justice, compensation structure, empirical review of the relationships among the variables were assessed. The study is influenced by the theoretical framework of social exchange theory. This study employed a quantitative research design based. The population of the study was 2711 from the six Higher Educational Institutions (HEI) owned by Gombe State. The sample size was 338 while the sample size was calculated based on Krejcie and Morgan (1970), The data analysis was conducted through statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics and structural equation modeling (SEM) with Analysis of Moment Structure (SEM-AMOS) by using SPSS software-version 23. Findings from the study indicated that, procedural justice and compensation structure were reported to have significant and positive relation with job satisfaction while distributive justice and interactive justice reported to have insignificant relation with job satisfaction. These results suggest that Government should follow open and fair procedures, offer workers a voice, meet regularly, conduct employee surveys and keep an on-open door policy. Government must work to distribute the functions, tasks and duties equally, fairs have fairness of outcome, in addition to developing appropriate rules and regulations in order to have fairness of decision making, lastly Government should care about their employees and build good employee communication.

Introduction

Studies in human resource management and organizational behavior have focused considerable attention on the concept of organizational justice due to its relationship with several work-related outcomes, including job performance, commitment, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), job satisfaction, perceived organizational support, and turnover (Arab & Atan, 2018). Human resources are an important factor in an organization. The organization will be able to conduct its organizational activities with the support of its human resources. Employee job satisfaction is a very important factor in an organization which drives the achievement of organizational goals. Successful organizations put employee job satisfaction ahead of students satisfaction, knowing that satisfied employees satisfy students, produce higher quality products, achieve and sustain high work productivity, and stay with the organization (Mardanov, 2020), "Job satisfaction is based partially on what one feels and partly on what one thinks". Job satisfaction became the most widely used measure of happiness in the happy.

Higher Educational Institutions play a crucial role in educational, technical, social and economic wellbeing of a country. The role of staff in the achievement of these purposes cannot be overemphasizing. Both academic and non-teaching staffs play a crucial role in the operation of academic institutions. They represent a significant investment for the institutions. Higher Educational Institutions need workers who are satisfied with their work, both now and in the future. However, the

nature of both work and organization has been in flux because of lack of feelings of fairness. So, it is important to study job satisfaction. Administrators, therefore, need to understand what factors influence staff in order to motivate them and improve their performance.

The concept of job satisfaction has been studied widely, and still receives attention in current research. When employees are both satisfied with their jobs and committed to the organization, the bond with the organization will be strengthened and will result in greater cooperation and a reduced likelihood of quitting. Staffs with higher satisfaction are more likely to behave with high productivity, less absenteeism, stress and resignation. Higher job satisfaction is also considered as an effective approach to retain and attract staff. Job satisfaction is important because it enhances employee morale, creates enjoyable relationships with co-workers, promotes creativity and innovation and encourages organizational citizenship behavior and influence organizational success. In addition, job satisfaction leads to increased employee retention, lower levels of absenteeism, higher productivity and better quality service.

Dissatisfied employees are more likely to seek opportunities elsewhere, resulting in a revolving door of talent. This turnover of workers can be costly for organizations in terms of recruitment and training expenses and the loss of institutional knowledge and experienced personnel (Langhneja, 2023). In a toxic work environment, employees may feel isolated, unsupported, and disconnected from their colleagues. A study by Gallup found that 70% of employees are disengaged at work, leading to decreased productivity levels and a higher rate of absenteeism (Vaid, 2023). Job satisfaction plays a very important role in the workplace for both employees and businesses. Staffs that are happy in their jobs will have a better quality of life than those who aren't, and businesses who keep their staff happy will often see a plethora of positive effects in the workplace. A more detailed focus on job satisfaction shows that employees may be satisfied with some aspects of the job, but not with others (Fennell, 2021).

Satisfied employees are also more committed to their organization (Farrington & Lillah 2018). Many factors have been researched on job satisfaction. For example, intrinsic and extrinsic and conflict (Mardanov, 2020), distributed leadership (Torres, 2018), trust and information networks (Aziz *et al.*, 2021) and compensation (Ashraf, 2020). Although there are studies on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction in the prison service (Sembiring *et al.*, 2019), organizational justice and work outcome in Iraq (Arab & Atan, 2018), and organizational justice and police job involvement, the researcher could not find a study on organizational justice and job satisfaction in Higher Educational Institution (HEI) settings in Nigeria.

Organizational justice is an important area of research in human resource management and organizational behavior since the 1990s although its origin is traceable to longer periods. Indeed justice in organizations has considerable appeal just as in society as a whole. Organizational justice affects the life, relationship, and wellbeing of the workforce and the individual worker. The perception of justice is important as it can affect the management by affecting performance and engendering counterproductive behavior and workplace conflict (Woldearegay, 2021). Organizational justice may also affect staff attitudes, intentions, and behaviors (Lambert *et al.*, 2020).

Justice induces voluntary and proactive attitudes and actions for members of an organization, and has an important influence on the stability, maintenance, and performance of the organization. The members form exchange relationships based on efforts made to achieve the goals of the organization and subsequent results; throughout this process, the members continuously evaluate and respond to whether the results given to them (i.e. rewards, responsibilities, promotions, incentives, and special vacations) are higher or lower than their expectations (Yu *et al.*, 2019).

However, of recent staff have been witnessing instances of lack of fairness such as lack of transparency in performance appraisal and feedback, inconsistent promotion, nepotistic allocation of offices and responsibilities, irregular distribution of benefits, work overload, absence of a strong mechanism for grievance redress, improper working conditions and lack of participation in decision making which may result to employee turnover intentions (i.e the total number of workers who leave the organisation over a certain time period includes those who exit voluntarily as well as employees who are fired or laid off that is, involuntary turnover).

These findings underscore the importance of addressing key factors like fair wages, career development opportunities, internal promotion pathways, and supportive work environments to mitigate turnover intentions among employees in different industries. These issues are consistently affecting their job satisfaction and job outcomes. In the face of these issues, research on organizational justice and job satisfaction are confined to banking, IT and manufacturing sectors (Karem *et al.*, 2019).

To determine the effect of the relationship, the following hypotheses were stated:

H₀₁: There is no positive and significant relationship between Distributive Justice and Employee Job Satisfaction among Higher Educational Institutions of Gombe State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between Procedural Justice and Employee Job Satisfaction among Higher Educational Institutions of Gombe State.

Ho3: There is no positive relationship between Interactive Justice on job satisfaction among Higher Educational Institutions of Gombe State.

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between Compensation Structure and employee job satisfaction among Higher Educational Institutions of Gombe State.

2. Review of Literature

Employees' Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an important work attitude for both staff and their employing institutions. Job satisfaction is the pleasurable or positive emotional feelings a worker has about his or her job experiences in relation to previous experiences, current expectations, or available alternatives. It is also 'the extent to which people like or dislike their jobs' (Lamond, *et al.*, 2017; Spector, 1997) Job satisfaction results when employees' appraisals of their job experiences fulfill their employment-related wants and needs and lead to a positive emotional states (Lambert *et al.*, 2020). Job satisfaction is associated with reduced work absenteeism, lower levels of job burnout, decreased turnover intent/turnout, increased support for educational programs, higher life satisfaction, greater commitment to the organization (Keena *et al.*, 2020), an increased likelihood of engaging in pro-social work behaviors (i.e., going above what is expected), greater creativity and support for organizational change and improved performance (Woldearegay, 2021).

Organizational Justice

Organizational justice is one of the most frequently researched areas in human resources management, organizational psychology and organizational behavior. Organizational justice represents an employee's perception of justice in a workplace. It is defined as "the degree to which individuals believe that the outcomes they receive and the way in which they are treated by an organization are fair, equitable and in line with expected moral and ethical standards" (Barau, 2018). Perceived organizational justice refers to anyone's subjective perceptions of the fairness of allocations (Chetty, 2018). Organizational justice influences organizational commitment, organizational citizenship, job satisfaction, and performance (Colquitt, 2001; Swalhi *et al.*, 2017).

Organizational justice has been researched widely in relation to subjectivity (Barau, 2018), decision making (Eberlin & Tatum, 2008), emotional exhaustion (Hur *et al.*, 2015), whistle blowing (Hur *et al.*, 2015), and cognitive outcomes (Katsumi *et al.*, 2019). Employees expect just treatment from the organization and the leaders to which they devote their time and energy (Barau, 2018). The concept of justice (i.e., fairness) is an important part of society. Organizational justice refers to the perception that the employing organization treats employees in a fair and just manner (Colquitt, 2001) (Lambert *et al.*, 2020). Justice is glue that holds people together and allows them to work effectively, whereas injustice can pull them apart. Organizational justice or injustice is a major part of job resources because of its potential for supporting or hindering the motivation of employees to achieve goals and their awareness of learning and growth in the organization (Ren *et al.*, 2021).

Distributive Justice

This refers to employees' perceived fairness about work outcomes. The performance outcomes include pay, performance rating, promotion, power sharing, prestige, and outcomes of dispute resolutions. Thus, employees experience distributive justice when they perceive that they are receiving sufficient return from social and economic resources (Fujimoto *et al.*, 2013; Rai, 2013; Barau, 2018). Distribution should be based on a transparent upholding of established criteria. It relates to the morality of the distribution of "burdens and benefits". Distributive justice is more salient in affecting the personal outcomes of an individual, such as satisfaction with payment.

Distributive justice is based on perceptions of equity rather than equality. Equality refers to all employees experiencing the same outcomes regardless of their efforts or contributions to the organization. In contrast, equity refers to the situation when a specific employee's outcomes depend on his or her efforts and contributions to the organization. According to the equity exchange principle, employees assess organizational outcomes based on individual inputs (i.e., contributions), comparing their inputs and outcomes relative to other employees to determine whether they are being treated fairly. In other words, distributive justice is based on the equity exchange principle. That is, people compare what they (and others) have done in exchange for what they (and others) have received in order to determine whether or not the outcomes are perceived as just (Ajzen, 2020). The distribution will be just, when the most qualified and successful employee is promoted.

Procedural Justice

This refers to employees' perceived fairness about the authority's decision-making processes, and the HR policies and practices and processes that subsequently affect their work outcomes (Fujimoto *et al.*, 2013). Procedural justice focuses on the organization's decision to impose punishments and distribute rewards such as pay raises promotion and performance appraisal ratings. (Hur *et al.*, 2014; Singhry, 2018)found a significant relationship between procedural justice and job performance.

Most employees want the processes and procedures used to determine distributive outcomes to be consistent, open, and fair, regardless of the result. The process can be as important as, or even more important than, the outcome itself. For example, the perceived fairness of employee evaluation procedures is important for employees, regardless of whether their performance appraisals were negative or positive. Employees are concerned with the processes by which outcomes are determined. While some desirable outcomes can be reached using unfair processes, these unfair processes will bias the outcome against some individuals, thus rendering the entire process unjust. Procedural justice is not only focused on the allocation of compensation and the organization's decision-making process but also on the way to identify their presence, which is an important factor for organizational engagement (Jang *et al.*, 2021). Thus, it can be seen that procedural justice has a stronger relation to process and objective than distributive justice. It has been argued that when employees find the process of HRM practices fair, then they are more likely to find the outcomes of these practices to be equitable. Six rules that people use when assessing procedural justice: consistency, bias suppression, accuracy, correct ability, representativeness and ethicality.

Interactional Justice

This refers to 'employees' perceived fairness about the quality of interpersonal treatment that employees receive from an authority'(Le *et al.*, 2020). It relates specifically to how fairly management distributes communication opportunities and how the quality of supervisor employee communication is perceived by employees. It addresses the issue of how respectfully managers communicate with subordinates and how fairly they distribute communication opportunities among subordinates. Interactional justice is divided into interpersonal justice and informational justice.

Compensation structure

Compensation is the combination of all cash incentives and the mix of fringe benefits that an employee receives from a company and it constitutes an individual employee's total compensation (Ashraf, 2020). Compensation structure includes items such as retirement (pension and gratuity), health insurance, life insurance, disability insurance, paid leave, paid holidays, flexible scheduling, and educational assistance to name a few. These benefits bind an employee to the employing organization and result in a strong job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Compensation can be categorized as intrinsic or extrinsic, financial or non-financial and direct or indirect benefits, which influence job satisfaction and ultimately organizational commitment. Evidently, compensation has an important link between the rewards a company offers and those individuals who are attracted to the compensation into working for the organization and those employees who will continue the work for the business (Devonish, 2018). Generous rewards and incentives tend to retain people because high rewards lead to enhanced job satisfaction, organizational commitment and company loyalty (Ashraf, 2020).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Proposed framework of Organizational justice and job satisfaction

Source: Adapted from the work of Ashraf *et al.*, (2020), Dhaouadi & Sliti, 2020; Niehoff & Moorman, 1993).

The above figure shows the hypothetical relationship between the independent variable (Organisational Justice) and the dependant variable (Job Satisfaction). It also shows the direction of the relationship among the variable under review.

Empirical Review

Organizational Justice and Job Satisfaction

Li *et al.*, (2020) develop an integrated model of the relationship between hotel employees' organizational justice perception and job performance. The model is examined using a valid sample of 303 hotel employees in 4 hotels located in Zhaoqing, one of China's top tourist cities. The basic data is acquired and the Structural Equation Model (SEM) method is adopted to conduct empirical tests of the integrated model. The study found that the four dimensions of organizational justice have significant and positive effects on employee satisfaction, and indirectly affect job performance through employee satisfaction.

Distributive Justice and Job Satisfaction

Mylona & Mihail, (2019) explores how employees' performance in the public sector is affected by perceptions of organizational justice in terms of resource allocation (e.g., benefits and compensation). The responses received from a sample of 490 employees working for public organizations in Greece indicated that work performance is significantly and positively related not only to employees' satisfaction with pay, but also to employees' perceptions of distributive and procedural justice. Model suggests that the relationship between organizational justice (distributive and procedural) and work performance (work effort and work quality) is fully mediated by pay satisfaction. In particular, it is indicated that organizational justice is positively related with pay satisfaction. The study did not indicate the tool used in data collection for the study, but the study can be replicated to enhance the employees job satisfaction in the study area.

Interactive Justice and Job Satisfaction

Zahednezhad *et al.*, (2020) tested a hypothetical model linking various dimensions of organizational justice to the job satisfaction and nurses' intention to leave the profession based on the theoretical assumptions of the Alexander model of voluntary turnover. A cross sectional survey methods of 317 inpatient ward nurses of six teaching hospitals in Tehran, Iran during 1 September 2017–14 November 2018 were conducted. Clinical nurses were recruited by a multistage random sampling. Data were collected using structured questionnaires of organizational justice, job satisfaction, and nurses' intention to leave. Data were analyzed by structural equation modeling using Amos 22 statistical program. The structural equation model demonstrated adequate fit and the hypothesized correlations were partially supported. The findings suggested that the distributive justice ($p < .001$; $\beta = 0.24$) and interactional justice ($p < .001$; $\beta = 0.44$) could indirectly affect the nurses' intention to leave the nursing profession via the direct impact on job satisfaction. Furthermore, distributive and interactional justice could reduce the intention to leave the nursing profession by influencing the job satisfaction of the clinical nurses.

Compensation Structure and Job Satisfaction

Singh & Tiwari, (2021) investigated the relationship between compensation management and employees' job satisfaction in Nigeria's Insurance Sector. The instrument used in information gathering was questionnaire. In all, 250 questionnaires were administered to the employees' of an insurance company, 213 were retrieved and 212 were found usable for response rate of 84.4%. The statistical analysis revealed that compensation management and employees' job satisfaction are significantly correlated though weak and that compensation management has an impact on motivation and job satisfaction of employees'.

Social Exchange Theory

This study is influenced by the theoretical framework of Zahednezhad *et al.*,(2020). This study aims to test a hypothetical model linking various dimensions of organizational justice to the job satisfaction and nurses' intention to leave the profession based on the theoretical assumptions of the Alexander model of voluntary turnover. This study is influenced by the organizational justice theory proposed by Kreitner & Kinicki (2014); Sembiring *et al.*, (2020) It states that organizational justice has three different components, i.e. distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice. Distributive justice reflects the perceived fairness of how resources and rewards are distributed or allocated. Procedural justice refers to the perceived fairness of the processes and procedures used to make distribution decisions. Interactional justice is related to the quality of interpersonal treatment received by members.

According to the social exchange theory, negotiated exchanges between employees and employers form the basis of social relationships (Blau, 1964). It is suggested that workers exchange their inputs (physical and mental effort, skills, time, etc.) for specific incentives that the organization provides (salary, benefits, as well as intangibles such as recognition, respect, reputation, and status). It represents employee's mental tally of the "give and take" of the

employment relationship. In line with the theory, behavioral responses to justice perceptions have been described as manifestations of social exchange at the work- place (Mylona & Mihail, 2019).

3. Methodology and Data collection

This study employed a quantitative research design based on descriptive survey method. The survey adopted a cross-sectional strategy where questionnaires were given to respondents only once. The entire staff of Gombe State Higher Educational Institutions (HEI) constituted the population of the study. Gombe State Government has six existing Higher Educational Institutions (HEI) within the State. The total population of the study is two thousand seven hundred and eleven (2,711) for the six institutions which consists of GSU (1469), CONS (108), GSPB (271), COELSN (219), COEB (402) and COHSTK (242) respectively. This study used Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Table for the determination of sample size. Based on the staff population of 2,711, the sample size will be 338, comprising of 183, 14, 34, 27, 50 and 30 for the six Higher Educational Institutions respectively. The respondents will be selected through a proportionate random sampling technique of the four categories of staff in the six Higher Educational Institutions in Gombe. Data was obtained with the aid of a structured questionnaire. While AMOS SEM Version 23 was used to analyzed the collected data. This technique used has become imperative due to the fact that, this study involves a structural model which serve as most suitable way to evaluate the fit of the proposed model (Hoyle, 1995).

4. Result and Discussions

Figure 1: Measurement Model combining all the Constructs after the re-specification was made

AMOS Output Version 23.0, (2024)

Table: 2 Assessment of the fitness Indexes of the entire Constructs.

Name of category	Name on index	Index Value
Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.065
Absolute fit	GFI	0.902
Absolute fit	NFI	0.933
Incremental fit	CFI	0.960
Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	2.386

Source: AMOS Output, Version 23.0 (2024)

The measurement model for the entire construct after the re-specification was made. To ascertain the level of correlation between and among the construct, literature recommended that, for any correlated construct with a value higher than 85% (0.85), either of the two constructs should be dropped, as ‘one is a mirror to the other’. Looking at the values in the measurement model, the highest and the least correlated values were 83% (0.83) and 12% (0.12) between PJ & JS, and DJ & IJ respectively. Table 3 below, indicated the fitness indexes achieved as shown.

Structural Model Evaluation
Structural Model for the overall Variables

Source: AMOS Output, Version 23.0 (2024)

Table: 3 Result of Hypotheses Testing of Structural Modelling

Path relationship	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P. V.	Result
DJ → JS	0.005	0.047	0.111	0.912	Accepted
PJ → JS	0.667	0.081	8.215	***	Rejected
IJ → JS	-0.051	0.030	-1.722	0.085	Accepted
CS → JS	0.266	0.083	3.210	0.001	Rejected

Source: AMOS SEM Output Version 23.0 (2024)

Table 3, shows the structural modelling results of hypotheses testing of Standardized regression coefficient among; DJ, PJ, IJ, and likewise, CS on their relations with JS. The result show that, DJ and IJ hypotheses were accepted (it accepted the null hypotheses), as their respective β values are; 0.005 and -0.051. While their CR are; 0.111 and -1.722. However, P values of the accepted hypotheses are; 0.912, and 0.085 respectively. However, hypotheses of others such as; PJ, and CS in relation to JS were all rejected (it accepted the alternate hypotheses), as their respective β values were; 0.667, and 0.266. Others were; CR= 8.215 and 3.210, with their respective P values of less than 0.001 and 0.001 respectively.

It is interesting to note that, among the four (4) hypotheses under study, only PJ & CS were reported to have significant and positive relations with Job satisfaction of the employees in tertiary institutions in Gombe state. This means that, when Employees' Job satisfaction move by 1%, PJ move by 67%, while CS move 27% as Employees' Job satisfaction move by 1%.

Note that, the value of R^2 for the entire contributions of the Four (4) variables studied in relations to Job Satisfaction among the Staff of Higher Institutions in Gombe State, is 71% as shown in figure 2. Although, this research has gotten 71% contributions on the dependent variable, but Procedural Justice contributed more than the Compensation Structure among the staff of the Higher Institutions under study, as their contributions were 65%, and 26% respectively. This suggested that, other researchers can as well look into other variables that can influence Job Satisfaction among the Staff of Tertiary Institutions in Gombe State, to ascertain the level, more than 71% to say, 100%.

5.1 Conclusion:

1. Procedural Justice and Job Satisfaction (PJ → JS):

The relationship between procedural justice and job satisfaction is highly significant ($p < 0.001$), with a strong positive estimate (0.667). This suggests that fairness in the processes and procedures within the organization, such as decision-making and resource allocation, strongly affects job satisfaction. Employees who perceive organizational processes as fair are likely to be more satisfied with their jobs.

2. Distributive Justice and Job Satisfaction (DJ → JS):

The path between distributive justice and job satisfaction is not significant ($p = 0.912$), with a very weak estimate (0.005). This indicates that distributive justice does not play a meaningful role in determining job satisfaction in this model. Employees' perceptions of fairness in outcome distribution (such as pay, rewards, and promotions) appear to have little influence on their job satisfaction.

3. Interactional Justice and Job Satisfaction (IJ → JS):

Interactional justice has a marginally negative effect on job satisfaction (estimate = -0.051, $p = 0.085$), though it is not statistically significant at the usual threshold ($p < 0.05$). This indicates a slight negative relationship, but the effect is weak and inconclusive. It suggests that how employees are treated personally by their supervisors and peers may have a minor negative impact on their job satisfaction.

4. Compensation Structure and Job Satisfaction (CS → JS):

The compensation structure is found to have a significant and positive effect on job satisfaction (estimate = 0.266, $p = 0.001$). This means that employees' perceptions of the fairness and adequacy of the compensation system are strongly related to their job satisfaction. A fair and competitive compensation structure enhances job satisfaction.

5.2 Recommendations:

Given the significant positive relationship between the procedural justice and job satisfaction, organizations should focus on ensuring that all organizational processes are transparent, fair, and inclusive. Employees should perceive that decisions affecting their roles (such as promotions, evaluations, and resource allocation) are made based on clear, consistent, and fair criteria.

Since distributive justice had no significant effect on job satisfaction in this study, it may not be as crucial in this context. However, it remains important to maintain a reasonable level of fairness in reward distribution to avoid potential dissatisfaction, especially in relation to pay and benefits.

While the effect of interactional justice is weakly negative, this still suggests a potential area for improvement. Organizations should invest in enhancing the way employees are treated by managers and peers. Training for supervisors on respectful communication, empathy, and fair treatment could improve job satisfaction.

As the compensation structure significantly influences job satisfaction, it is crucial for organizations to ensure that compensation is fair, competitive, and aligned with employees' contributions. A review of compensation policies, ensuring fairness in pay, benefits, and rewards, would likely boost employee satisfaction and retention.

Final Thoughts:

The results emphasize the importance of procedural justice and compensation structure in driving job satisfaction. Organizations that prioritize fair decision-making processes and equitable compensation systems will likely see higher employee satisfaction and engagement. However, attention should also be given to interactional justice to mitigate any negative effects on job satisfaction.

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